

Roadmap NFDI4Earth Pilots

1st Pilot Cohort April 2022 - March 2023

Empowering Earth System Science through Julia for Optimized Processing and Statistical Driver Attribution in Big Data

Pilot title	Statistical learning to assess the factors underlying environmental changes
Project Duration	06-2022 / 05-2023
Contributors¹	Daniel E. Pabon-Moreno ¹ , Gregory Duveiller ¹ , Markus Reichstein ¹ , and Alexander Winkler ¹
DOI	10.5281/zenodo.7995187
Corresponding author	Alexander Winkler (awinkler@bgc-jena.mpg.de)

¹Max-Planck Institute for Biogeochemistry, Jena, Germany.

Contributors	Contribution
Daniel E. Pabon-Moreno	Conceptualization, Formal Analysis, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Software
Gregory Duveiller	Conceptualization, Formal Analysis, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing
Markus Reichstein	Funding acquisition
Alexander Winkler	Conceptualization, Formal Analysis, , Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition

Date of submission: 01 of June, 2023

This work has been funded by the German Research Foundation (NFDI4Earth, DFG project no. 460036893, <https://www.nfdi4earth.de/>).

Abstract

The availability of remote sensing information of the Earth has increased exponentially over the last decades. This trend is expected to continue as new remote sensing products from new satellite missions become available. To keep the pace with the amount of information gathered by the various sensors orbiting the Earth, it is essential to develop tools that allow scientists and students to easily manipulate and perform operations on spatio-temporal gridded data. Ideally, the new generation tools should be able to run, and interact with data on cloud platforms rather than individual computers. In this pilot, we developed a new Julia package as an entrance point to high-performance computing based on the YAXArrays.jl package, the YAXArraysToolbox package. The front-end of the YAXArraysToolbox package is divided in two modules, the first one (Basic Operations) contains a set of basic operations to process and visualize large gridded data in a very efficient way. The second module (Spatio-Temporal Analyses) contains a set of tools to perform data-driven attribution, e.g., using the space-for-time concept, and spatio-temporal data partitioning for cross-validation analyses. We anticipate that the package will be beneficial to various domains within the Earth system data science, and Julia user communities by providing a user-friendly environment. Advanced users will also benefit by taking advantage of the implemented analyses to perform data-driven attribution using machine learning techniques and semi-empirical modeling. We intend to further enhance the capabilities of the package by incorporating additional functions useful for statistical driver attribution in large datasets, including forward feature selection based on regularized regression.

I. Introduction

The availability of Earth observational (EO) datasets, such as those obtained through remote sensing, has experienced a remarkable surge in recent decades. This trend is expected to continue as new satellite missions and other EO campaigns are introduced. These extensive collections of multiple datasets, such as those housed in the Earth System Data Laboratory (ESDL), provide valuable insights into the widespread and persistent changes occurring within the Earth system. However, it gets increasingly complex to handle the vast amounts of data and uncover the underlying causes of these observed changes. To keep pace with the vast amount of gathered data, it is crucial to develop new approaches to statistical driver attribution for these EO datasets. In addition, tools that enable scientists and students to easily manipulate and analyze spatio-temporal gridded data are necessary. Ideally, these tools should be applicable to data available on cloud platforms, such as the ESDL, thereby eliminating the need for maintaining software on personal computers and facilitating data accessibility.

In this pilot project, we have developed a new Julia package called `YAXArraysToolbox.jl`, which builds upon the `YAXArrays.jl` package. It serves as a foundation for various statistical driver attribution algorithms while seamlessly integrating with high-performance computing (Figure 1). The package enables scientists to efficiently perform generic operations, such as temporal aggregates and maskings, in a user-friendly manner (Figure 2). We have implemented two distinct approaches to statistical driver attribution / spatio-temporal data analysis and plan to include two additional algorithms (Figure 3). The infrastructure provides a direct entry point for the user to implement his*her own algorithm. To test our package and workflow, we have focused on addressing the question of driver attribution for surface temperature changes related to land-cover changes observed by satellites (Figure 4).

By leveraging the `YAXArrays.jl` backend and the Julia ecosystem, we anticipate that the scientific community, particularly in climate and Earth system data analysis, will benefit from this package as part of the 2Facilitate initiative within NFDI4Earth. While the pilot project has a specific use case for land-atmosphere interactions, driver attribution plays a crucial role in many other geoscientific disciplines, such as oceanography or solid earth research. This project particularly focuses on the interoperability element of the FAIR principles, facilitating the integration of data with applications or workflows for analysis, storage, and processing. The pilot project ensures that the developments surrounding data cubes in NFDI4Earth align well with international initiatives on handling large gridded data. In the future, we plan to expand the capabilities of the package to include more advanced statistical algorithms based on machine learning techniques. These may involve spatio-temporal folds for cross-validation, forward feature selection, and methods adapted from the CAST (Caret Applications for Spatio-Temporal models) R package. Overall, this pilot project addresses the following aspects:

1. The scientific context of this pilot project revolves around the increasing availability of EO data and the need to develop efficient tools for manipulating and analyzing spatio-temporal gridded data to conduct efficient and robust statistical driver attribution using observational data.
2. At the beginning of the pilot project, the research data management challenge was dealing with the overwhelming amount of EO information and the necessity for user-friendly and efficient tools to handle this data. State-of-the-art solutions were limited, and scientists often had to resort to writing time-consuming custom code for inefficient data operations.
3. The proposed solution to this challenge was the development of a new Julia package, the YAXArraysToolbox.jl, which leverages optimized workflows and serves as a front-end to the YAXArrays.jl package. This package provides scientists with a set of common functions for spatio-temporal data and driver attribution analysis, integrating with the Datacubes Julia infrastructure (e.g., ESDL).

II. Results

1) Implemented Solution

The YAXArraysToolbox.jl package allows users to efficiently process and visualize large spatio-temporal gridded data. The backbone of the package is the YAXArrays.jl package that allows to easily and efficiently apply functions in large gridded datasets that cannot be loaded into RAM. The YAXArrays.jl package also allows users to easily upscale analysis from laptops to clusters without the necessity to re-write code. However, we consider that functions and analyses that are generic enough can also be part of the Julia Data cubes ecosystem in a new package. The YAXArraysToolbox.jl functions on which users interact do not follow the YAXArrays.jl style, but instead focus on ready to use functions similar to those found in the Raster package of the R ecosystem. For visualization, the YAXArraysToolbox package relies on the Makie ecosystem, specifically, for plotting maps, relies on the GeoMakie package. The YAXArraysToolbox.jl package is structured in three main modules (Figure 1) where one of the modules connects to the YAXArrays.jl package. The users will interact with the modules “Basic operations” and “Spatio-temporal analysis/functions”. In the “Basic operations” module, the user will be able to apply functions to easily manipulate, and visualize large gridded data (Figure 2). In the spatio-temporal analysis module, scientists and students can easily perform different analysis to evaluate the relationship between different variables present in large gridded data. So far in the Spatio-temporal module we make available two techniques. The first one is the space-for-time technique (space4time) introduced in the field of geoscience by Duveiller et al., (2018). The space4time technique estimates the average change of local climate if the land cover changes from one class

to another. For example, savannas are usually hotter than neighboring forest, then contrasting the local climate conditions we can evaluate the potential effect of the transition from forest to savannas. This allows to partially attribute observed changes in surface temperature to changes in land-cover. The second technique is the spatio-temporal folds generation presented by (Meyer et al., 2018). Spatial and temporal autocorrelation can produce bias when evaluating the performance of statistical models. For this reason, it is necessary to implement cross validation strategies that consider the spatial and temporal context when defining folds for training and testing models. The spatio-temporal cross validation scheme implemented in the YAXArraysToolbox package allows the user to define three strategies: Leave-Location-Out (LLO), Leave-Time-Out (LTO) and Leave-Location-and-Time-Out (LLTO) as proposed by (Meyer et al., 2018).

Figure 1. YAXArraysToolbox package dependencies.

*Only one method implemented that allow to extend values to a match the temporal resolution of a second cube.

Figure 2. YAXArraysToolbox package. Basic operations module. Structure and functions.

Figure 3. YAXArraysToolbox package. Spatio-temporal analysis module. Structure and functions.

We are planning to submit a technical note in *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*, presenting the package and showing examples of how to use the `space4time` analysis and the basic functions already implemented in the package.

To give an idea of the current capabilities of the package, we prepare a series of Jupyter notebooks showing how to use the package. In the [notebook 1](#), we present how to plot time series and maps from data cubes. We also show how to aggregate data and apply mask by time

and space dimensions. In a case study, we evaluate the effect on land-surface temperature caused by changes in vegetation cover for the African continent (for details see: [notebook 3](#), Figure 4). Our results show that in most areas the transition from evergreen broadleaf forest into croplands leads to an increase of local land-surface temperature change of 1 to 3 Kelvin. Spurious and mixed signals might occur due to quality issues in the land-surface temperature dataset within the Earth System Data Cube v2, used in this case study. As a proof-of concept of the space4time technique presented in [notebook 2](#), we prepare an example that shows how the space4time technique is able to disentangle and attribute the signal induced by transitions of land cover classes. For the k-fold generation that takes into account spatial and temporal correlation, we prepare the [notebook 4](#) explaining how to use the function.

Figure 3. Changes in land-surface temperature (LST) attributed to transitions from evergreen broadleaf forests to croplands using the space4time technique

2) Data and Software availability

The YAXArraysToolbox.jl package is publicly available on Github: <https://github.com/dpabon/YAXArraysToolbox.jl> under the GPL-3 license. The package is also available on Zendo with the DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7989936>. The README file of the package mentions how to install the package where to find the documentation and the links to the tutorials (Jupyter notebooks) <https://github.com/dpabon/YAXArraysToolboxNotebooks>. The tutorials are also available on Zenodo with the DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7990052>.

While developing the pilot we had the opportunity to contribute to other projects and communities. For example the documentation of the YAXArrays.jl package:

- <https://github.com/JuliaDataCubes/YAXArrays.jl/issues/188>
- <https://github.com/JuliaDataCubes/YAXArrays.jl/pull/203>

The functionality of the YAXArrays.jl package:

- <https://github.com/JuliaDataCubes/YAXArrays.jl/issues/159>
- <https://github.com/JuliaDataCubes/YAXArrays.jl/issues/192>
- <https://github.com/JuliaDataCubes/YAXArrays.jl/issues/198>
- <https://github.com/JuliaDataCubes/YAXArrays.jl/issues/216>
- <https://github.com/JuliaDataCubes/YAXArrays.jl/issues/237>

The functionality of the DiskArrays.jl package:

- <https://github.com/JuliaDataCubes/YAXArrays.jl/commit/5aac674d93bcecf4aa6543306ae11f9933df3cf3>

The functionality of the Raster.jl package:

- <https://github.com/rafaqz/Rasters.jl/issues/367>

The functionality of the Quarto project:

- <https://github.com/quarto-dev/quarto-cli/issues/4594>

Interaction with the Julia community:

- <https://github.com/JuliaDataCubes/YAXArrays.jl/issues/217>
- <https://discourse.julialang.org/t/what-is-the-difference-between-the-two-methods-of-lm-on-glm-jl/95140>
- <https://discourse.julialang.org/t/how-to-make-a-south-up-map-using-geomakie/96438>

3) Innovation and FAIRness

On one hand, Julia has been an outstanding programming language in terms of speed and usability. On the other hand, the YAXArrays.jl package is a powerful tool to process large gridded

data. Nevertheless, the writing style of YAXArrays functions can be challenging for novel users of Julia or in general to users coming from R and Python ecosystems. The YAXArraysToolbox.jl tries to simplify the use of YAXArrays.jl implementing functions that follow the style of the Raster R package where the users do not start writing their own functions but running many common operations already implemented in the package. This approach should facilitate to get started with data analysis in the Julia ecosystem in an efficient manner – a key contribution to NFDI Consortium Earth System Sciences. The YAXArraysToolbox package is distributed under GPL v3 license, ensuring that the code will always remain open and free to be modified by other users. The package is properly versioned, where each one of the changes on each one of the versions is clearly stated. Finally, The releases are linked to the DOI publication in Zenodo ensuring that the users can cite the package in their publications.

III. Challenges and Gaps

We have identified a crucial gap in efficiently analyzing large Earth Observation (EO) datasets and extracting cause-and-effect relationships for driver attribution. To address this challenge, we have chosen to leverage the power of the Julia language. Its efficiency aligns perfectly with the requirements for EO analysis and seamlessly integrates with the Earth System Data Laboratory, also implemented in Julia.

Implementing the full functionality of the package as proposed in the pilot was not possible, mainly due to time constraints. It is important to stress that building a package in the Julia ecosystem also means contributing to other packages by reporting bugs, providing ideas and helping to diagnose errors. While this approach may slow down the package development process, it is a win-win for the community, increasing the robustness of the packages, and stability of the same, and also contributing to the culture of free software. Developments for the Julia ecosystem are an investment that will pay off for the scientific community in data analysis on the long run.

We have experienced several gaps in the statistics packages that need to be better established in Julia. For example, the ability to efficiently run linear regressions in loops. We have also experienced some bottlenecks when using moving windows in the YAXArrays package, which should be solved with the new implementation of the DiskEngine package. From our perspective, the more people use these packages, the faster and more robust they will become. Currently, one of the main challenges is to convince students and scientists of the benefits of migrating and contributing to the Julia ecosystem. We expect that this gap to narrow exponentially over the

next few years as more professors, students and researchers slowly start to migrate their analysis and code to Julia.

IV. Relevance for the community and NFDI4Earth

We expect that thanks to the YAXArraysToolbox package more people will be able to manipulate, analyse, and visualize large gridded data in an efficient and user-friendly way. We consider that our package can be an entry point to the JuliaDataCubes infrastructure for environmental scientists, developers coming from R or Python ecosystems, and students that are learning to use programming languages. We also expect that scientists will be able to take advantage of these optimized tools included in the spatio-temporal analyses when evaluating the relationship between different variables in space and time, and conduct driver attribution based on large gridded datasets. When connected to cloud computing facilities, such as the ESDL hosting a variety of observational datasets, these developments can contribute to a significant improvement in the workflow of data analysis in Earth system science. The YAXArraysToolbox package is designed to be used by students, climatologists, ecologists, geocologists, and in general anyone working with large gridded spatio-temporal data.

In the README file of the package we have mentioned the procedure for reporting bugs, suggesting new ideas or formulating questions. We plan to provide support for at least three years while we continue to develop the package. So far we have not included the package in the Julia general register, so it is not widely known in the ecology and Earth system science community yet. Nevertheless, we are in contact with colleagues at the University of Hamburg who are already using our package for their analyses.

V. Future Directions

As shown in Figure 2, there are techniques that are highly relevant for the application of machine learning for spatio-temporal data that need to be developed within the package. The first one is the Forward Feature Selection (FFS, Meyer et al., 2018), where machine-learning models are trained using all the possible pairs of variables, and then some measure of importance of the individual variables is estimated using a spatio-temporal cross-validation scheme. The process continues by iteratively adding new variables to the first model, until the model performance does not increase anymore. The second method is the area of applicability (Meyer & Pebesma, 2021), where geographic areas (different from those used during training) are identified to make predictions while maintaining an error similar to that estimated during the training process. To estimate the area of applicability a dissimilarity index is estimated as suggested by the authors. We plan to develop and implement these functions next year. On the side, we also plan to improve the overall functionality of the package by adding a function, where the user can choose between "space", "time", or "balance" optimization strategies to automatically select the chunk

sizes after each YAXArraysToolbox operation. If this approach is well received by the community, we plan to backport it to the YAXArrays package. From a technical point of view, we still need to develop an approach to create spatio-temporal folds using lazy views of the cubes, and not just on DataFrame objects. To achieve this, it is already planned to migrate the YAXArray data object to DimensionalData for details see: <https://github.com/JuliaDataCubes/YAXArrays.jl/pull/249>.

One of the issues when working with gridded data is that cubes assume a Euclidean space of latitude and longitude which introduces geometric artifacts. For example, a 5 by 5 pixel window does not cover the same area at the poles as it does in the tropics. To solve this issue and produce equal areas regardless of the location of the window, it is necessary to represent the Earth as a sphere. This approach will be developed over the next two years as part of the Open Earth Monitor project: <https://earthmonitor.org/>. We expect that with this new approach, we will be able to move from moving windows to moving hexagons or triangles with the same area.

The next step for the YAXArraysToolbox package is to get the critical mass to improve the stability of the same. When the DiskArrayEngine package (<https://github.com/meggart/DiskArrayEngine.jl>) is ready we will have to rewrite some functions as this new package is expected to break parts of the code on YAXArraysToolbox. In terms of scientific progress, we plan to evaluate the changes in biophysical variables caused by changes in land cover classes for Africa using new geostationary satellites to better track the diurnal cycle. For this study we will use the space4time technique and the forward feature selection analysis. In the medium term, we expect that the YAXArraysToolbox.jl package can be backported to the Rasters.jl package to avoid fragmentation. Nevertheless, the current implementation of Rasters.jl does not rely on YAXArrays.jl to do perform calculations. However, internal plans are to make this transition in the coming months. Then we will be able to migrate the functionality of YAXArraysToolbox.jl into Rasters.jl, at least for the basic operations modules. Given the nature of the spatio-temporal analysis module we plan to keep these functions in the YAXArraysToolbox.jl package, while continuing to develop and support the package as shown in Figure 2.

In summary, all developments undertaken in this pilot and planned for the next three years (funded by the Open Earth Monitor project), will enable researchers to analyze big data efficiently using the power of Julia. The functionality provided in our package provides the opportunity to extract cause-and-effect relationships from large observational datasets with ease and effectiveness.

VI. References

Duveiller, G., Hooker, J., & Cescatti, A. (2018). The mark of vegetation change on Earth's surface energy balance. *Nature Communications*, 9(1), Article 1. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-017-02810-8>

Meyer, H., Reudenbach, C., Hengl, T., Katurji, M., & Nauss, T. (2018). Improving performance of spatio-temporal machine learning models using forward feature selection and target-oriented validation. *Environmental Modelling & Software*, 101, 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2017.12.001>

Meyer, H., & Pebesma, E. (2021). Predicting into unknown space? Estimating the area of applicability of spatial prediction models. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*, 12(9), 1620–1633. <https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.13650>